

COIL Project Group 8

DRAUGHTMASTER
FRESH PRESSED BEER

Written report on findings

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I. Introduction

In this paper, we analyze whether and how Carlsberg should enter the US market with its DraughtMaster system. For this purpose, the "Drexel University" and the "Berlin School of Economics and Law" conducted a qualitative study. "The DraughtMaster is a complete beer delivery system that uses concepts from the so-called circular economy to operate. The goal of the DraughtMaster is to reduce environmental impact while also providing organizational efficiency. It contains two central innovations, the kegs are made of plastic instead of metal, and the CO₂ gas component is replaced by another mechanism."

Our goal is to give Carlsberg a recommendation and to formulate conditions under which a market launch can succeed, so that this does not fail. Throughout our research we had the ability to ask very specific questions and receive very specific feedback across the board. Furthermore, we will show which additional criteria still need to be included and where Carlsberg needs further study data.

II. Methodology:

Before we start with the actual results, this part is dedicated to the analysis, with the question of how we collected data, how we proceeded and why we chose the appropriate method.

Our project is a collaboration between Drexel University in Philadelphia and the Berlin School of Economics and Law. This intercultural cooperation is intended to ensure that experience from markets (Germany and the USA) can be incorporated into the project and that results can be recorded for specific market conditions. In order to be able to give Carlsberg recommendations, we have taken a qualitative research approach. This method has the decisive advantage that the industry can be better understood and that it is possible to talk to the participants in sufficient depth and thus test hypotheses. In contrast, quantitative approaches can provide less information about the background of the data, the participants reply. In conducting the research, we formed 10 different groups. Each of these groups conducted three different interviews. Two of them with B2C consumers (one person in the US and one in Germany) and one interview with a B2B representative (either from Germany or the US). For the B2B representative, we made sure that the person had enough experience in the restaurant industry (e.g. bar owner, manager). This was to ensure sufficient validity. (i.e. the absence of systematic errors due to unsuitable interview partners should be excluded). The questions were in-deep questions, if possible, no simple yes-no questions, but questions where the interviewee had to answer in detail. For both B2B and B2C, the questions focused on general attitudes toward beer and sustainability. In the case of consumers, however, the focus was on personal beer consumption, while in the case of B2B the focus was on the technical devices of the beer dispensing system and the supply chain. The goal here was to comprehensively find out how consumers and B2Bs feel about seamlessness in the beer industry. The questions were structured similar to an hourglass. At the beginning, the questions were very general (e.g., consumers were asked about their

drinking habits) and then became more and more specific (e.g., what types of beverages are drunk and what is the attitude of B2B/B2C to sustainability). After that, the questions became more general again. In order to achieve sufficient reliability (free of random errors), all interviews of the 10 groups were included in the subsequent analysis. Thus, our qualitative analysis is based on a total of 30 interviews. For safety, all interviews were recorded to avoid any ambiguities. Afterwards, all interviews were typed up in text. Each group then recorded the most important information from their interviews and made it available to all the other groups.

III. Findings:

Through the method described above, we were able to distil five findings which in turn influence the recommendations for the market launch and which should therefore be included in the evaluation:

Finding 1: The Use of Plastic is Conflicting to Business Owners

Throughout the research and interview process, our findings have highlighted that the current DraughtMaster system is seen to have multiple drawbacks. Firstly, B2B consumers have a variety of concerns regarding the fact that the keg is plastic because of plastic waste and the difficulties in the recycling system. The use of plastic is conflicting due to the amount of time it takes to break down even when recycled. When interviewed, a waiter stated, “Plastic is difficult to recycle, and the kegs are not reusable. I don't feel comfortable. It also depends if the plastic is really recycled.” In addition to the concern about whether plastic is actually more sustainable, there is a clear concern on how to recycle the system and if it's actually being done correctly. Business owners also mentioned that they don't necessarily connect plastic usage as being a positive aspect. One stated, “I really don't understand one aspect of this. Nowadays we are trying to distance ourselves from plastic, plastic straws are banned and now we want to exchange the barrel for plastic too? For me, this is not a particularly original path. Just why? Doesn't make sense to me.” Society in general is moving towards a plastic free lifestyle due to past negative impact by the material. Individuals feel conflicted about how beneficial it would really be to reintroduce it to their business. Business owners also questioned where the plastic goes after the keg is empty and if they would have to dispose of them themselves.

Additionally, we found that B2B consumers prefer reusing over recycling. The DraughtMaster is a single use system. There is a lack of knowledge of how the DraughtMaster gets recycled and if the process is actually effective. Overall, there is an uncertainty on the right disposal when the kegs become empty, questioning the true effectiveness of the system. Due to this, consumers expressed that they would be more inclined to stick to their traditional keg which is known to be reusable

Finding 2: Sustainability Alone is not Enough for Business Owners

Although there is an importance of sustainability understood by consumers and the industry, sustainability alone is not enough for business owners to utilize the DraughtMaster System. In this industry, most consumers do not choose their beer to drink or bar to go to based on how sustainable it is. Customers don't care much about the draught system which is used. Most do not even care enough to ask or would not let this change which bar they go to. Business owners believe that the sustainability factor could potentially attract tourists but not enough to make a viable difference. We found that main paying points of customers include price, taste, and known branding. In terms of the taste, there is a concern for the change in taste and also a disquiet about the DraughtMaster actually tasting better enough to be worth switching to. Business owners and staff are hesitant to blindly switch over without knowing how consumers will react to the change in taste. Especially since this hasn't been an ongoing issue they've noticed in the past. This mindset is also shown by the Director of Operations of a Berwyn PA bar that stated, "if it ain't broke, don't fix it" Business owners believe that their customers are already accustomed to the traditional system and the change is too big of a risk. Consumers come in to get regional beverages in which they prefer the taste and origin over how sustainable beer is drawn from a tap. They already know what they like and how much they're willing to pay for it.

Finding 3: Business Owners are Concerned about Added Costs

There is also a worry of an added cost if the taste does not align to what individuals are used to. A business owner in Quakertown PA expressed that he would be open to the idea of switching but his main conflict would be cost. He expressed that most establishments already have keg rooms that they've invested loads of money on. Additionally, businesses currently already have well developed relationships with local vendors that they receive deliveries from. Acquiring a new system that is yet to be proven to do well with their customers is a huge risk that could be detrimental. For this reason, business owners are skeptical about making the switch until they're able to first hand see the benefit in costs and customer reactions.

Finding 4: The German and US Market have Differentiating Needs

Overall, through our findings we were able to draw the conclusion that while draft beer is key for both markets, different markets have different concerns and pain points. Germany has many small businesses that focus on tradition. During our interviews, a German Business Owner stated "I don't know if the system is beneficial for Germany, we have a good reuse/recycling system of the aluminum barrels, combined with low transportation ways, due to local breweries and regional ingredients the old system is better for the environment." They prefer to serve local beer and prioritize taste over most other factors. Their customers value good, fresh tasting beer. These consumers also have very strong

brand loyalty. Large beer producers serve mostly only big events in Germany. Due to this, a change in system would be a huge adjustment for this market. Whereas we found that the US market does not prioritize tradition as much. As much as there are well known beer brands, their consumers are much more open minded and willing to try something new. The US also does not have as good of a reuse system currently put into place so a sustainable option is definitely more of interest to business owners.

IV. Recommendations:

When going through our findings, it was evident that there are some steps that can be taken from the Carlsberg side to establish a better connection with the customer while also staying true to their own brand.

Recommendation 1: Use Direct comparison to attract customers

A lot of the DraughtMaster's systems benefits are underwhelming when not directly compared to the current system the consumer is using. A way to show the customer the true benefits of this system would be to directly compare it to the current system. An efficient way to do this is by offering free testing to consumers so that they are able to establish for themselves whether the system is right for their business. Rather than telling the benefits, it would be more beneficial to the company to show them in comparison to regular beer, for example they should make it clearer and more explicit that they pollute 40% less CO₂ than regular beer. Letting the customer get a free trial would in turn help them see the benefits both financially and in their own product of the difference between reusing and recycling and why recycling would be the better option for the environment.

Recommendation 2: Keep the switching costs low

Training their employees to learn how to remove the kegs or even clean them is an upfront cost that the owners have to pay in order to have their employees trained. According to our findings, a way for Carlsberg to make their system more beneficial for the customers would be to provide the training that is needed to use the DraughtMaster system free of cost. This would lead to lower switching costs, since the cost to train the employees has been taken out of the owners hands. Once the owner is confident that they don't have to incur an extra cost to train their employees, they would be more likely to use the DraughtMaster system compared to if the training was an expense that the owner would have to take on.

Recommendation 3: Focus on B2B Customers

The biggest focus for Draughtmaster right now should be with the B2B customers. Our analysis shows that customers don't care much about the draught system and their system

would mostly be implemented with the B2B customers. The results and research show that they need to focus their distribution efforts on the B2B customers. Local pubs and breweries in the US would be more susceptible and accepting to using a system like DraughtMaster because there isn't really a regional beer culture where most pubs get their beer from a regional brewery like there is in countries in Europe i.e. Germany, England. Also, as our research shows, the customers in the American market that these businesses get aren't usually as traditional with their take on beer and are already used to the big brands like Carlsberg, AB etc.

Recommendation 4: Different approaches for Different markets

Staying linear with their approach to their product is important for Carlsberg, but where they should diversify their efforts is to try and develop different advertisements and outlooks when trying to enter different markets and for different target groups. Highlighting the right aspect of their system when entering a market that cares more about the sustainability aspect than the ease of installation can be important and vice versa. This would lead to a more varied presence and more room for developing their products vision while also catering to each of different customers needs.

V. Conclusion

As mentioned previously the goal of our research was to attempt to be able to give recommendations for the start of bringing DraughtMaster to the US. What we took you through was an in depth look at what it takes in order to come up with those recommendations. Which are keeping the cost low for customers, focusing on B2B customers, showing the benefits in a direct opposite system to the current system, and having different advertisements for different markets. Each of these recommendations were founded by using extensive qualitative research, and each of them must be things the marketing team looks at when figuring out how to implement the DraughtMaster in the US. Our final recommendation is that Carlsberg should enter the market in the US, but have to do more research, because our research can't provide all the insights. For example, we did not have quantitative data on the general competitive situation and market share, as well as price levels. In addition, Carlsberg should consider our recommendations, especially the focus on B2B customers in marketing, since B2C customers have too little interest in the actual supply and beer tap method.